

THE IMPORTANCE OF ETHICAL STANDARDS AND VALUES IN THE PROFESSIONAL SOCIALIZATION OF THE FUTURE TEACHER

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Annotation

In the article, the position of the teaching profession in society based on educational reforms, the importance of moral standards and values in the legal socialization of future teachers based on the acquisition of moral qualities, the content of moral standards, the content of the teacher's professional qualities are highlighted based on the approaches of scientists. In the teaching profession, the formation of the skills and competencies of mastering behavior and practical application to pedagogical activity, the basis of the social norms set by society, the professional mechanism and components are mentioned.

Keys words: socialization, moral norm, value, professional adaptation, professional virtue, behavior, ethics, social norm, adaptation mechanism, reflexive-evaluation mechanism, creative mechanism, emotional-volitional component, value-motivational component, activity component, evaluation component.

Introduction

New Uzbekistan "Strategy of Development" initiated the third renaissance of the new stage of our national development. The third renaissance recognized the issues of promotion, protection and implementation of human rights as the most priority direction of our reforms, and among several directions, the important tasks of legal socialization among the population and young people were taught to the minds of the young generation about rights and duties, defines the importance of deeply inculcating the concepts of honesty and purity as well as norms of manners, forming the legal culture of young people based on the history, religion, traditions, and national values of the Uzbek people. This is a global education on the basis of setting priorities for the systematic reform of higher education before representatives of the pedagogical field, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, sets the goal of training competitive pedagogues who can meet the standards and standards of society.

As an active participant in the legal policy of the state, the future teacher must strictly observe the rights of the participants of the educational process, protect their interests, understand the legal basis of regulating social relations, and have a positive experience of participating in legal relations. requires that they acquire, understand the personal meaning of legal behavior, acquire socially significant legal knowledge and skills, and have practical application skills in professional and personal activities. The process of mastering certain professional knowledge, skills and abilities of a person requires mastering professional experience, standards and values of the professional community. A person's acquisition of a profession, entry into a professional environment, and implementation of accumulated professional experience include the norms and values of professional ethics.

Methods. Moral norms are evaluated by civil society depending on its level of development. Some authors distinguish between "moral standards" which are the leading principle of morality and specific moral standards that arise from it.

Examples of the highest standards of morality are Thomas Aquinas' authorial standard "Aim for good, avoid evil", Jeremiah Bentham's principle of seeking "maximum benefit for the maximum number of people", or Albert Schweitzer's principle of "respect for life" [4].

Psychologist Michelle Gelfand points to the connection of moral standards with a certain national culture (the theory of "cultural rigidity-freedom").

The teacher performs a responsible task: not only teaching (developing intellectual abilities, imparting certain knowledge), but also educating a new generation. Therefore, an important component of the professional socialization of a modern teacher is his spiritual and moral culture and ethics.

The teacher participates in the process of reproducing the moral consciousness of the person not only individually, but also through the teacher and student teams, and the parent team. In doing so, he acts as the collective bearer of public morality. Now it is more important than ever to talk about the moral side of the teacher's professional culture, because only a teacher who embodies the model of a high moral personality can successfully solve the complex tasks of reforming general education and vocational schools. It is culture and high morals that make a teacher a person.

Ethics (Greek: ethika, from the word ethos - custom) is a philosophical science, the object of study of which is morality, its development, norms and role in society. Professional ethics is one of the main theoretical foundations of any professional activity [12]. "The philosophical doctrine of ethics, its development, principles, norms and roles in society; a set of behavioral norms"[11] (S.I. Ozhegov).

V.A. As Sukhomlinsky noted, a teacher becomes a pedagogue only after mastering the best tool of education - morals and ethics. Without knowing the theory of ethics, it is impossible to have a full professional training of a teacher today. Only a teacher who embodies the example of a high moral person can successfully solve the complex tasks set before the reform of the general education and vocational school.

Only a teacher with impeccable morals can reveal the beauty of human actions to students, teach them to distinguish kindness from benevolence, pride from arrogance. In pedagogical ethics, special attention should be paid to the essence and specific characteristics of the individual moral consciousness of the teacher. This is reflected in his behavior.

Legal socialization of a person - the process of developing ideas about a person's social role and place in society plays an important role in the formation of a teacher's behavior. Legal socialization works as a component of a single socialization process. Socialization is the development of society's social norms, values, ideas, rules, behavior and stereotypes of understanding.

Social norms are rules of behavior established and accepted historically in society, which regulate relations between people. The existence of social values and norms is an integral feature of any society.

Discussion. In the process of legal socialization of future teachers, mastering of professional behavior and the formation of skills and competencies for practical application to pedagogical activities are based on social norms determined by society. Also, in turn, social norms require the future teacher to follow the norms of behavior in the regulation of

relationships between people in his professional development. The teacher always works as a carrier of a certain professional culture, which determines the level of his professional competence, the system of value directions of individual and personal manifestation. As the teacher acquires new roles, the teacher enters new social and cultural situations, he develops abilities, skills and professional qualities as ways to achieve certain goals, in which personality and individuality, their integration, already begin to manifest.

The teacher's professional behavior often has a situational and educational character, it shows the situation of students, teachers, their expectations and attitudes in a certain period. Taking into account the factors of legal socialization of future teachers, we consider the basis of professional behavior - the value model of professional behavior based on professional-pedagogical culture, self-awareness and reflecting the value directions and meanings of professional activity. mission, manifested in professional actions.

Valued behavior is related to meeting the need for ethical guidelines for professional activities and life activities. Valued behavior system is based on pedagogical values. It is based on the axiological potential of a person, his desire for moral perfection. The teacher's professional behavior reflects three groups of values as follows: values-goals (individual and social), values-means (personality, individuality of the teacher and student) and organizational values. As E. N. Gusinsky and Y. I. Turchaninova noted, all the values of education can be divided into the values of preserving the existing order of things and the value of changing it.

Valuable behavior ensures the stability of a person, continuity of behavior, determines the direction of needs and interests. The integrity and stability of the value system determines the maturity of a person. Values serve as long-term strategic life goals and life's main motivations. They define the moral foundations and principles of behavior.

As the authors note, the values and meanings of educational activities are beyond the boundaries of any specific pedagogical or psychological discipline studied by the teacher in the process of professional training. In the relationship between the teacher and students, the main values are manifested, on the one hand, the teacher's personality, and on the other, the educational system. They can be in harmony, but they can also be in severe conflict.

Social behavior is related to the achievement of the goals of professional activity and is manifested in the teacher's direction, ability and competence, which reflects the characteristics of the interaction between the teacher and students in the process of joint activity. The basic unit of professional behavior is social action. A teacher is a representative of a social group, a carrier of group values, image and lifestyle. The basis of social behavior is the teacher's communicative potential. In the process of communication, two cultures, two worlds meet; it creates a socio-pedagogical resonance that determines the direction of the subject's development, an important example of a high value that wants to imitate appears in everything - behavior, passion and professional characteristics.

One of such personal formations is attitude, social habits, skills, behavior patterns. It can be noted that there is a certain connection between social relations, customs and norms.

E. M. Penkov believes that social custom is a factor that strengthens the content of some social norms in the individual mind and behavior of people. The norms of behavior are fixed in the psyche of a person in such a way that when implementing them, he may not know the social nature of his actions, their connection with the interests of society and other people. In this case, the habit frees a person from repeatedly referring to his mind, building a mental

model of his behavior each time, giving it a preliminary assessment, etc. Many human actions occur as a result of habits. It is done automatically in everyday life. This is manifested in the form of the following mechanisms of professional development based on the structural and functional analysis of the future teacher's subjectivity.

Adaptation mechanism - ensures the adaptation of the future teacher to the conditions of pedagogical activity and the formation of socially approved behavior in this pedagogical team. Habits, norms, teachers' values, social relations and stereotypes may dominate here.

The mechanism of reflexive evaluation is the realization of individuality, originality, taking responsibility for oneself, manifestation of situational activity, conflict with generally accepted values on the way to achieving common goals, with the presence of a critical position. depends. the person himself, professional reality, mechanisms of creating his own forms of activity.

The creative mechanism provides a way out of psycho-physiological and socio-cultural destiny, which ensures extreme individuality, that is, personal growth, and is manifested in activity above the situation, innovative activity.

From a broad social point of view, professional development, on the one hand, the professional formation of an individual, on the other hand, the social development of an individual, reflects the process of mastering social experience, values, norms of behavior, professional qualities, which in the future teaching activity is important. Professional and personal qualities of a teacher are a set of socio-psychological formations that have a factor influence on the professional result of a teacher [10, p. 186] (N.E. Shchurkova).

"Professionally important qualities of a person mean anatomical, physiological, psychological and social qualities of a person as a labor subject" [13] (V.V Kozacha S.V Tarasov, E.I Garber). "Under professionally important qualities, he understands the individual characteristics of the subject of activity that affect the effectiveness of the activity and the success of its development" [6, p. 59] (V.D. Shchadrikov).

E.G. Romitsina "Under the professional qualities of a teacher, he understands a set of universal, professional-branch and professional-specific qualities that affect the effectiveness of his professional activity and serve as internal conditions for the formation of competence" [7, p. 28].

T.R. Narulina "The teacher's professional qualities mean a set of individual qualities of the teacher that ensure the successful implementation of changing activities in a changing cultural and technological environment, designing the system and sequence of students' actions and their own actions. The experience of organizing collective and group joint activities, building a trajectory of professional and personal self-development and forming it as a subject of technological development[8, p.56] suggests.

Professional formation is one of the important aspects of personal development, and it expresses the needs and interests of a person only related to the choice of labor and professional activities. (general development expresses the complex of all needs, the system of his relations with existence, surrounding people, and himself [9, p. 36] (N. Muslimov).

N.M. Egamberdiyeva proposes to use the concept of "professional maturity" from the point of view of personal and professional socialization of students and cites its essence as follows: professional maturity is the orientation of education in such a way that it is understood by students as a subject of professional activity, one's own professional development, while emphasizing the need to plan career goals and own methods of achieving

them. In the process of research, the system of pedagogical components of legal socialization of future teachers based on moral norms and values was determined (see Figure 1).

- **emotional-volitional component** (the presence of positive emotions for professional activity, self-confidence, the ability to set and solve tasks);
- **value-motivational component** (interest, value directions, meanings, attitude to activity, attitude to success in the profession);
- **the activity component** (the ability to determine the goals, tasks and stages of the activity, the use of tools and technologies based on personal capabilities and resources);
- **evaluation component** (ability to evaluate results and self-evaluation, make corrections and eliminate deficiencies).

Figure 1. System of pedagogical components for legal socialization of future teachers.

As a result of the theoretical analysis of scientific evidence, future teachers should master the norms of professional standards. To solve this problem, in 2013 E.A. Yamburg was the first to develop a scientifically based professional standard of standard qualities that a modern teacher should possess. According to the author of this project, the teacher's professional standard should fulfill a number of important tasks:

- to be a means of implementing an educational strategy in a changing world;
- to be a means of improving the quality of education and bringing local education to the international level;
- to be an objective measure of the teacher's qualification;
- to serve as a means of selecting pedagogical personnel in educational institutions;
- to be the basis for concluding an employment contract defining the relationship between the employee and the employer.

In conclusion, we can say that legal socialization of future teachers on the basis of moral norms and values is the most important element of the development of professional qualities, in the process of assimilation of systematized knowledge based on moral norms and professional values. The acquisition of ethical standards and professional values is a theoretical and cognitive activity, which includes the acquisition of knowledge, skills of a legal

nature - knowledge of law, legal values, principles, norms, skills and abilities, analysis , consists of transferring, collecting and mastering the skills to use them. This knowledge is manifested in real life, professional activity, as well as in the practice of its implementation, as the ability to use one's rights, observe prohibitions and fulfill obligations. The acquired knowledge should become an internal need and habit to be a legal activist in relation to personal confidence, strict compliance with the requirements of the law, and then compliance with the norms of the law. Formation of teacher's professional qualities on the basis of ethical standards and professional values consists in transferring acquired knowledge to value relationships, turning them into internal confidence, giving them a positive emotional color and strengthening them in legal habits that become a motive for legal behavior.

References:

1. Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". // National database of legal documents [in Uzbekistan]
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5618 "On fundamental improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society". National database of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 10.01.2019, No. 06/19/5618/2452, 11.12.2019, No. 06/19/5892/4134; 09.10.2020, No. 07/20/4857/1357. [in Uzbekistan]
3. Abdullah Sher. Ethics. -T. 2000, -15 p [in Uzbekistan]
4. Biesaga T., Norma moralności, [w:] A. Maryniarczyk (red.), Powszechna Encyklopedia Filozofii, t. N, Lublin: Polskie Towarzystwo Tomasza z Akwinu, 2000 [dostęp 2015-04-25].
5. Ossowska M., Normy moralne. Próba systematyzacji, Warszawa: PWN, 1970 [in Russian]
6. Shadrikov V.D. Problemi sistemogeneza professionalnoy deyatel'nosti. - M., 1997 [in Russian]
7. Romitsina YE.G. Razvitiye professionalno znachimix kachestv pedagoga-psixologa v sisteme povisheniya kvalifikatsii: avtoref. dis. ... kand. ped. nauk. - Maykop, 2007 [in Russian]
8. Narulina T.R. Razvitiye professionalno znachimix lichnostnix kachestv budushego uchitelya texnologii: avtoref. dis. ... kand. ped. nauk. - Irkutsk, 2009. [in Russian]
9. Muslimov N.A. Theoretical-methodical foundations of professional formation of vocational education teacher: Doctor of Pedagogy... diss. - T., 1993. - page 364 [in Uzbekistan]
10. Shurkova N.YE. Pedagogicheskaya technology, M.: Pedagogicheskoye obshestvo Rossii, 2002. P. 186. [in Russian]
11. <https://bokshic.slutsk-vedy.gov.by/>
12. Pedagogicheskie_tekhnologii//tekhnologijaindividualizacii_obuchenija_inge_unt_a_s_granic_kaja_v_d_shadrikov/12-1-0-58#.
13. https://www.sovremennye_obrazovatelnye_tehnologi.ru/ [http:// moi-rang. ru./publ/ methodicheskie_materialy/](http://moi-rang.ru/publ/methodicheskie_materialy/).
14. <http://www.eidos.ru/journal/2005/0910-12.htm>. - V nadzag: Tsentr distantsionnogo obrazovaniya "Eidos", e-mail: list@eidos.ru
15. <https://textarchive.ru/c-2720412-p24.html>